

Efficiency and profitability of an IPM package against insects, blast, and nematodes in irrigated rice

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In Burkina Faso, major biotic constraints to rice production in irrigated conditions include insects, diseases, and nematodes. Lepidopterous stem borers (*Chilo zacconius*, *C. diffusilineus*, *Maliarpha separata*, and *Sesamia calamistis*) can cause up to 33% yield losses (Dakouo et al 1991). A 1% increase in damage of the African rice gall midge is correlated with a 2% yield loss (Nacro et al 1996). Pot trials showed a yield loss of 30% caused by rice root nematode *Hirschmaniella spinicaudata* (Thio 1992). Rice blast (caused by *Pyricularia oryzae*) causes yield losses with an estimated value of more than US\$10 million in West Africa (WARDA 1995). Pest control in irrigated rice still largely depends on the use of chemicals without meeting the necessary criteria of efficiency and profitability for small-scale farmers. Therefore, a cost-effective integrated pest management (IPM) package was developed by a multidisciplinary team to minimize reliance on toxic and expensive chemicals. This IPM package combines the use of local natural products made of organic manure (5 t ha⁻¹) against nematodes, rice straw ash (2.5 t ha⁻¹) against blast, dry neem (*Azadirachta indica*) leaf powder against nematodes, and alcoholic extracts of neem seed powder (200 g into 0.25 L of alcohol and 0.75 L of water) against insects. The efficiency and profitability of the package were evaluated during the 2000 wet season

at two irrigated rice schemes, Banzon and Karfiguéla, near Bobo-Dioulasso, southwest Burkina. Its efficiency was optimized with the use of a rice gall midge-tolerant variety, BW 348-1. The IPM package (T3) was compared with two other treatments, T1 and T2. The first treatment (T1) was the control with no products against pests. T2 was a reference chemical treatment combining the insecticide Basudin (diazinon) at 1,000 g ai ha⁻¹ in foliar sprays at 20, 40, and 60 d after transplanting (DAT), the nematicide Basamid (dazomet) at 100 kg ha⁻¹ (incorporated into the soil 14 d before transplanting), and the fungicide Kitazin (di-isopropyl-s-benzil-thiophosphate) in a foliar spray at 720 g ai ha⁻¹ at panicle emergence. The experimental design was a completely random-

ized block with three treatments and four replications, a plot size of 60 m² (10 × 6 m), and plant density of 25 × 25 cm. Insect damage (deadhearts and onion shoots) was assessed at 40, 60, 80, and 100 DAT. Foliar blast was evaluated at 35, 49, and 63 DAT and neck blast incidence at 15 and 30 d after panicle emergence (DAPE). Nematode populations were estimated at the time of Basamid application—before transplanting and at 30, 60, 90, and 120 DAT.

Pest damage was low with significant differences between treatments only at 60 DAT for insect damage and nematode populations, and at 30 DAPE for neck blast incidence (Table 1). There was no significant difference between treatments at Banzon for deadhearts and onion shoots. At Karfiguéla, reference chemicals

Table 1. Efficiency of an integrated pest management (IPM) package combining organic manure, rice ash, and neem products against nematodes, blast, and insects at Banzon and Karfiguéla irrigated rice schemes (Burkina Faso) during 2000 wet season.

Treatment	% deadhearts ^a (60 DAT)		% onion shoots ^b (60 DAT)		Neck blast ^c incidence (%) (30 DAPE)		Nematodes g ⁻¹ roots (60 DAT)	
	Banzon	Karfiguéla	Banzon	Karfiguéla	Banzon	Karfiguéla	Banzon	Karfiguéla
T1—Control, not treated	5.3 a	4.1 a	0.4 a	11.9 a	8.0 ab	10.1 a	11 a	22 a
T2—Reference chemicals	3.8 a	1.4 b	0.7 a	6.0 b	5.7 b	8.1 a	8 c	5 b
T3—IPM package	2.1 a	1.7 b	0.3 a	5.9 b	11.4 a	11.7 a	11 a	7 b

^aDeadhearts = damage caused by lepidopterous stem borers. ^bOnion shoots = damage caused by the African rice gall midge *Orseolia oryzivora*. ^cNeck blast caused by *Pyricularia oryzae*. Numbers followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level. DAT = days after transplanting, DAPE = days after panicle emergence.

(T2) and the IPM package (T3) were significantly different from the control (T1) with deadhearts reduced to 2.1% in T3 (IPM) compared with 5.3% in T1. Onion shoots decreased significantly to 5.9% in T3 compared with 11.9% in T1. Foliar blast incidence was low in all treatments and locations. There were significant differences between treatments for neck blast incidence only at Banzon; this incidence was significantly higher in the IPM plots (11.4%) than in the reference chemical plots (5.7%) and control (8%). The nematode population (per gram of roots) declined significantly from 22 in T1 to 7 in T3 and 5 in T2 at Karfiguéla. At Banzon, the control and IPM plots were significantly different (11 nematodes) from the reference chemical plots (8 nematodes).

The profitability of the IPM package is shown in Table 2. T2 gave a benefit of \$142.10 vs \$858 treatment cost at Banzon compared with \$231.90 vs \$858 at Karfiguéla. T3 resulted in a benefit of \$142.10 vs \$42.80 treatment

cost at Banzon compared with \$65.60 vs \$42.80 at Karfiguéla. The imported and expensive chemicals used in T2 led to economic losses with a cost-benefit ratio of 1 to 0.16 at Banzon and 1 to 0.27 at Karfiguéla. The IPM package made of local natural products provided a relevant cost-benefit ratio of 1 to 3.38 at Banzon and of 1 to 1.50 at Karfiguéla, with a double advantage in monetary gain and environmental protection.

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Table 2. Profitability of an IPM package combining organic manure, rice ash, and neem products against nematodes, blast, and insects at Banzon and Karfiguéla irrigated rice schemes (Burkina Faso) during 2000 wet season.

Treatment	Yield (t ha ⁻¹)		Benefit ^a		Cost of treatment ^b		Cost-benefit ratio ^c	
	Banzon	Karfiguéla	Banzon	Karfiguéla	Banzon	Karfiguéla	Banzon	Karfiguéla
T1—Control	6.3 b	5.8 b	—	—	—	—	—	—
T2—Reference chemicals	7.5 a	7.7 a	142.10	231.90	858.00	858.00	1:0.16	1:0.27
T3—IPM package	7.5 a	6.3 a	142.10	65.60	42.80	42.80	1:3.38	1:1.50

^aBenefit = (Yield treatment – Yield control) × \$121.43, where \$121.43 is the sale price of 1 t rice. ^bCost of treatment includes only the cost of synthetic pesticides in T2 and of raw material in T3. ^cCost-benefit ratio = return for every dollar invested. US\$1 = 700 FCFA.

Golden apple snail damage in Philippine Seed Board rice varieties

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Before a line is released to farmers, it undergoes rigorous evaluation of its reaction to various biotic and abiotic stresses across seasons and locations. However, rice varieties have never been evaluated for resistance to golden apple snail (GAS), *Pomacea canaliculata*, because all rice varieties were assumed to be equally

susceptible to this pest. Rice is at risk from GAS during the first 15 d after transplanting. Newly transplanted rice seedlings are devoured from the base. After complete removal of leaves and leaf sheaths, the plant cannot regenerate. The degree of damage depends on GAS density and size. The rapid spread of GAS and the

consequent losses make GAS management urgent. Commercial synthetic molluscicides are widely misused by rice farmers in an attempt to control GAS. To reduce the hazards of pesticide misuse and cost of control, identifying rice varieties less prone to GAS damage is important. Thus, this study examined rice variet-